

Stochasticity and chemical signal divergence in island lizard populations

Authors

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Quick instructions to reproduce the analysis

- Download “**data_and_code.zip**”
- Unzip the file, which includes the following objects:
 - ✓ “**data**” folder, including all the datasets needed to run the analysis;
 - ✓ “**SDSPAGE**” folder, including images of the electrophoretic gel used to characterize the protein profile of the secretions, together with an excel spreadsheet with notes about the samples (not needed to run the analysis);
 - ✓ Two numbered R scripts (“**01_among population chemical comparison.R**”; “**02_multiple regression on distance matrices_MRM.R**”), with the code to create the derived datasets, run the analyses, explore results, and produce plots. Detailed comments inside each script.
- Run the code files in the order they are provided and follow the instructions written in the code itself.
- Data and plots are created and saved in the working folder where you extracted the zip file.